

Time Management and Business Educators' Quality Service Delivery in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State

¹Joseph Odia, ²Odigwe Benjamin

¹(Ph. D.) Department of Business Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technology Education,
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State., Nigeria

Tel.: +2348067878917

²(Ph. D.) Department of Business Education Faculty of Vocational and Technology Education
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Tel: +2348037092010

Email: ogajoe4life@gmail.com, beodigwe2007@yahoo.com

Abstract

The study examined time management and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It specifically focused on the relationship between setting of clear goals, prioritization of tasks, creation of schedules, minimization of distractions, management of stress and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. The study employed a correlational research design. The population of the study was the 75 business educators in the four tertiary institutions currently running Business Education programme in Rivers State. The study was a census study as the total population of the study was used due to its manageable size. Therefore, no sampling technique was adopted. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers. The 75 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondent, and 68 copies were retrieved. Data collected was analysed with Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. Analysis of the data collected revealed that setting clear goals, prioritization of tasks, creation of schedules, minimization of distractions, and management of stress significantly affect Business Educators service delivery in tertiary institutions. Based on the findings it was recommended that: business educators should set clear goals to give them direction, motivation, and focus; business educators should prioritize their tasks for better time management; business educators should create schedules to provide a clear roadmap; business educators should minimize distractions to improve their quality of work; and business educators should manage stress to prevent physical and mental health problems caused by chronic stress.

Keywords: *Time Management, Business Educators, and Quality Service Delivery*

Introduction

Service delivery generally refers to the process of providing a service from a provider to a customer, encompassing all aspects from initial interaction to completion. Spacey (2016) defined service delivery as the process of providing customers with services. Quality simply means excellence and essential. Quality services delivery is the process of providing excellent, essential and peculiar services to customers or individuals in any organization. In the context education, business educators service delivery related to how business education lecturers provide education and support to students, including factors that impact their effectiveness and strategies for improvement. It involves ensuring that the service is delivered effectively, efficiently, and to the agreed-upon standards. Key elements include the quality, timeliness, and accuracy of the service provided. Quality service delivery is an important

tool needed for achieving the goals of education because students' learning outcomes are directly related to the quality of service offered by teachers. Towards quality service delivery, time management is inevitable.

Time management is the process of organizing and planning how to divide time between specific activities. According to Savino (2016), time management has also been defined as a form of self-management with a clear emphasis on time in understanding what activities to do; how to do them more efficiently; in what time it should be done and when is the correct time to the activity. Effective time management helps individuals prioritize tasks, minimize distractions, and complete work efficiently, leading to increased productivity and reduced stress. Key elements of time management include setting of clear goals, prioritization of tasks, creation of schedules, minimization of distractions,

and management of stress. These components work together to improve productivity, reduce stress, and ultimately lead to greater success in both personal and professional endeavours.

Setting of clear goals as a key element of time management involves defining specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound objectives. This approach ensures that goals are well-defined, trackable, realistic, aligned with overall objectives, and have a defined timeline. According to Rowe et al (2017) goal setting is described as the identification of a specific accomplishment to be made in a specific area with measurable outcomes, such as actions and timelines for achievement. The authors further said that goal setting is crucial for personal and professional development as it provides direction, motivation, and a framework for success. It helps individuals and organizations focus their efforts, measure progress, and achieve desired outcomes. By setting goals, individuals can enhance their performance, improve their focus, and cultivate a sense of accomplishment.

Prioritization of tasks involves deciding which tasks should be completed first based on their importance and urgency. This helps in efficient time management and ensures that the most crucial tasks are addressed promptly, leading to increased productivity and effectiveness. Joshua (2017) stated that prioritizing means to work with others to identify more critical and less critical activities and assignments, and to coordinate project assignments, roles and responsibilities, adjusting priorities when appropriate. Prioritizing tasks is crucial for effectively managing workload, reducing stress, and achieving goals (Joshua, 2017). By focusing on the most important and urgent tasks first, individuals can improve productivity, make better decisions, and feel a greater sense of accomplishment.

Creation of schedule in time management involves planning how to use time to achieve goals and priorities. This process typically includes identifying tasks, prioritizing them, estimating time for each, scheduling them, and then analysing and adjusting the schedule as needed. According to Bourne and Weaver (2018) schedule is a process that calls for the creation of guidelines and records for upholding, creating, managing, and controlling the time and resource schedules needed to complete a task. It helps service organizations to manage and allocate their resources. Hence, creating a schedule

can be proven a huge benefit for service organizations but it should be designed as per the needs of the organizations (Bounce & Weaver, 2018).

Minimization of distractions involves identifying, reducing, and managing factors that divert focus from important tasks, both internal and external. Effective strategies include creating a distraction-free workspace, managing notifications, limiting social media, and practicing mindfulness techniques. According to Leung (2015), distractions keep people from maintaining focus and productivity. In a study conducted to explore the effect of distraction on task performance and enjoyment among San Jose State University students, Leung found that participants who were promotion-focused performed better in mathematics compared to their prevention-focused counterparts (who aimed at preventing or avoiding failure) whether they were distracted by music or not.

Management of stress involves a combination of strategies focused on reducing exposure to stressors, altering employees' response to stress, and promoting overall well-being. Key approaches include identifying stressors, practicing relaxation techniques, maintaining a healthy lifestyle, and seeking support when needed. According to Lawrence and Melinda (2025), Managing stress is all about taking charge: of people's thoughts, emotions, schedule, environment, and the way they deal with problems. Lawrence and Melinda (2025) further opined that the goal is a balanced life, with time for work, relationships, relaxation, and fun as well as the ability to hold up under pressure and meet challenges head on.

Time management plays a crucial role in effective service delivery across various sectors, ensuring tasks are completed efficiently and on schedule. Effective time management practices, including planning, scheduling, and prioritization, positively impact service quality and overall performance. Studies have shown a strong correlation between time management and service delivery in areas like hospitality, education, and construction. For instance, a study conducted by Elenwo and Wike (2024) on time management as a correlate of quality service delivery in private secondary schools in Rivers South-East Senatorial District, revealed a significant positive relationship between time scheduling, priority setting, task delegation, and quality service delivery in private secondary

schools. Similarly, a study conducted by Marika et al (2021) on the influence of teacher time management practices on service delivery in public secondary schools in Kitui county, revealed a significant influence in proper time management practices and service delivery. Despite the positive impact of time management on service delivery in all sectors, problems like skipping of classes, poor lecture preparation, uninspired teaching methods, and a lack of commitment to research and student support are still very common in most schools today. It is against this background the seeks to examine time management and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Time management is crucial in the execution of any activity in organizations or institutions as it enhances productivity, reduces stress, and achieves goals effectively. It allows individuals to prioritize tasks, stay focused, and complete work efficiently, leading to a better work-life balance. By mastering time management, individuals can improve their decision-making, increase their confidence, and ultimately lead more fulfilling lives. Despite the positive role of time management in organizations or institutions, most employees including lecturers in tertiary institutions seemed to be exhibiting lackadaisical attitude towards managing their time for effective service delivery. This can be justified by series of complains by most students in tertiary institutions on lecturers' attitudes towards performing their tasks, as they are accused of skipping classes, not keeping to time schedule, and covering of large course contents within a very short period. This has impacted negatively on students' academic achievement, as it leads to students missing deadlines, increasing their stress and anxiety, and potentially leading to lower academic performance. Towards addressing these problems, numerous studies have been conducted which revealed positive relationship between time management and quality service delivery within and outside Nigeria. Majority of the of the studies so far conducted focused on secondary education. However, none of the studies has been conducted in higher institutions of learning in Rivers State. Hence, the study seeks to examine time management and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine time management and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, the study aimed at:

- a. examining the relationship between setting of clear goals and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- b. ascertaining the relationship between prioritization of tasks and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- c. examining the relationship between creation of schedules and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- d. finding out the relationship between minimization of distractions and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- e. ascertaining the relationship between management of stress and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between setting of clear goals and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between prioritization of tasks and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between creation of schedules and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between minimization of distractions and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
5. What is the relationship between management of stress and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is divided into three, which are content, geographical, and unit scope. The content scope of the study was limited to the specific purposes of the study which are the relationship between setting of clear goals, prioritization of tasks, creation of schedules, minimization of distractions, and management of stress and business

educators' quality service delivery. The geographical scope was limited to tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The unit scope of the study was limited to business educators.

Methodology

Design of the Study

The study employed a correlational research design. According to Devi et al (2022), correlational research refers to a non-experimental research method which studies the relationship between two variables with the help of statistical analysis. The

Table 1: Population Distribution of Respondents

S/N	Name of Institution	Population
1.	University of Port Harcourt Choba, Rivers State	16
2.	Rivers State University Port Harcourt, Rivers State	22
3.	Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt Rivers State	20
4.	Federal College of Education Technical Omoku, Rivers State	17
	Total	75

Source: Business Education Department of the various Institutions

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study was a census study as the total population of the study was used due to its manageable size. Therefore, no sampling technique was adopted.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers. The questionnaires titled: Time Management Questionnaire (TMQ) and Business Educators Quality Service Delivery Questionnaire (BEQSDQ) were divided into two sections. Section A contained the personal data of the respondents. Section B contained 30 items drawn from the specific purposes of the study with response options of 4 Likert scales of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments were validated by two professionals in the field of measurement and evaluation in the researchers' institution. Their

design is suitable for the study as it seeks to find out the relationship between time management and business educators' quality service delivery.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised the 75 (seventy-five) business educators in the four tertiary institutions currently running Business Education programme in Rivers State. The population distribution of the respondents is presented in table 1 below.

comments and corrections were considered in the final draft of the instruments to ensure their face, construct and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined with test re-test. It was performed by administering 10 copies of the instrument to ten business educators outside Rivers State twice within a space of two weeks. The results of the two tests were compared using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. A coefficient of 0.85 was obtained which made the instrument to be highly reliable.

Method of Data Collection

Data was collected through physical with the respondents. the 75 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondent, and 68 copies were retrieved. The 68 copies were used for the analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analysed with Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. To test for significance, the results of the tested hypotheses were interpreted based on Dana 2001 correlation decision framework. The decision framework include: 0.00-0.19 (very weak relationship); 0.20-0.39 (weak relationship); 0.40-0.59 (moderate relationship); 0.60-0.79 (strong relationship); 0.80-0.99 (very strong relationship); and 1 (perfect relationship).

Results

Research question one

What is the relationship between setting of clear goals and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

In response to the above research question, items 1 to 5 and items 26 to 30 of the questionnaires

administered to the respondents were used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 2 below.

Table 2: Analysis of the relationship between setting of clear goals and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (x̄)</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Setting of clear goals	68	3.294	0.830	0.059	0.914	Very strong relationship
Business educators' quality service delivery	68	3.088	0.989			

Source: Field work 2025

The above table revealed a calculated correlation coefficient (r) of 0.914. By using Dana 2001 correlation decision framework, 0.914 falls in the category of very strong relationship. Therefore, it is concluded that setting of clear goals as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Research question two

What is the relationship between prioritization of tasks and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

In response to the above research question, items 6 to 10 and items 26 to 30 of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 3 below.

Table 3: Analysis of the relationship between prioritization of task and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (x̄)</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Prioritization of tasks	68	3.221	0.944	0.044	0.939	Very strong relationship
Business educators' quality service delivery	68	3.088	0.989			

Source: field work 2025

The above table revealed a calculated correlation coefficient (r) of 0.939. By using Dana 2001 correlation decision framework, 0.939 falls in the category of very strong relationship. Therefore, it is concluded that prioritization of task as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Research question three

What is the relationship between creation of schedule and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

In response to the above research question, items 11 to 15 and items 26 to 30 of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: Analysis of the relationship between creation of schedule and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (x̄)</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Creation of schedules	68	3.147	0.738	0.071	0.902	Very strong relationship
Business educators' quality service delivery	68	3.088	0.989			

Source: field work 2025

The above table revealed a calculated correlation coefficient (r) of 0.902. By using Dana 2001 correlation decision framework, 0.902 falls in the category of very strong relationship. Therefore, it is

concluded that creation of schedule as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Research question four

What is the relationship between minimization of distractions and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

In response to the above research question, items 16 to 20 and items 26 to 30 of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 5 below.

Table 5: Analysis of the relationship between minimization of distractions and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (x̄)</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>r Value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Minimization of distractions	68	3.206	0.783	0.073	0.882	Very strong relationship
Business educators’ quality service delivery	68	3.088	0.989			

Source: field work 2025

The above table revealed a calculated correlation coefficient (r) of 0.882. By using Dana 2001 correlation decision framework, 0.882 falls in the category of very strong relationship. Therefore, it is concluded that minimization of distraction as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Research question five

What is the relationship between management of stress and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

In response to the above research question, items 21 to 25 and items 26 to 30 of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 6 below.

Table 6: Analysis of the relationship between management of stress and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (x̄)</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Management of stress	68	3.147	0.919	0.039	0.955	Very strong relationship
Business educators’ quality service delivery	68	3.088	0.989			

Source: field work 2025

The above table revealed a calculated correlation coefficient (r) of 0.955. By using Dana 2001 correlation decision framework, 0.955 falls in the category of very strong relationship. Therefore, it is concluded that management of stress as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of research question one provides answer the relationship between setting of clear goals and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was revealed that setting of clear goals as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. This finding agrees with the assertion of Rowe et al (2017). According to Rowe et al (2017) goal setting is crucial for personal and

professional development as it provides direction, motivation, and a framework for success.

Analysis of the second research question examines the relationship between prioritization of tasks and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was revealed that prioritization of task as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. The finding concurs with the postulation of Joshua (2017). Joshua (2017) postulated that prioritizing tasks is crucial for effective management of workload, reduction of stress, and achievement of goals.

Analysis of research question three provides answer to the relationship between creation of schedules and business educators’ quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was revealed that creation of schedule as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship

with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. The finding agrees with the opinion of Bounce and Weaver (2018). Bounce and Weaver (2018) opined that creating a schedule can be proven a huge benefit for service organizations, but it should be designed as per the needs of the organizations.

Analysis of research question four provides answer to the relationship between minimization of distractions and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The analysis revealed that minimization of distraction as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. The finding aligns with the assertion of Leung (2015). According to Leung (2015) postulated distractions keep people from maintaining focus and productivity.

Analysis of research question five provides answer to the relationship between management of stress and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The analysis revealed that management of stress as one of the key elements of time management has a very strong relationship with business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions. The finding agrees with the opinion of Lawrence and Melinda (2025). According to Lawrence and Melinda (2025) opined that the goal of stress management is to balanced life, with time for work, relationships, relaxation, and fun as well as the ability to hold up under pressure and meet challenges head on.

Conclusion

Time, they say is what we want most, but what we use worst. This proverb points out the irony of how people often complain about not having enough time, yet they are often the ones who waste it. This is the case of many organizations/institutions in contemporary Nigeria which is directly and indirectly affecting the productivity of many organizations. Hence, examining time management and business educators' quality service delivery in tertiary institutions is imperative. Quantitative analysis of the data collected revealed that setting clear goals, prioritization of tasks, creation of schedules, minimization of distractions, and management of stress significantly affect Business Educators service delivery in tertiary institutions.

Thus, it is concluded that effective and efficient service delivery in organizations/institutions largely depends on proper time management.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, the following recommendations were made.

1. Business educators should set clear goals to give them direction, motivation, and focus.
2. Business educators should prioritize their tasks for better time management.
3. Business educators should create schedules to provide a clear roadmap.
4. Business educators should minimize distractions to improve the quality of work.
5. Business educators should manage stress to prevent physical and mental health problems caused by chronic stress.

References

- Bourne L. M. & Weaver, P. (2018). The origins of schedule management: The concepts used in planning, allocating, visualizing and managing time in a project. *Front Engineering Management*, 5(2), 150–166.
- Devi et al (2022). Application of correlational research design in nursing and medical research. *DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/YRZ68*
- Elenwo, P. M. & Wike, R. E. (2024). Time management as a correlate of quality service delivery in private secondary schools in Rivers South-East Senatorial District, Rivers State. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 28-35
- Joshua, O. E. (2017). *Effective time management for high performance in organizations*. Lagos: The Nigerian Institute of Management Press.
- Lawrence, B. & Melinda, S. M. A. (2025). Stress management techniques and strategies to deal with stress. www.helpguide.org/mental-health/stress/stress-management
- Leung, K. (2015). The effects of distractions on task performance and enjoyment as moderated

by regulatory fit.
http://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/etd_theses/45
95

Rowe, D. A., Mazzotti, V. L., Ingram, A., & Lee, S. (2017). Effects of goal-setting instruction on academic engagement for students at risk. *Career Development and Transition for Exceptional Individuals*, 40(1), 25-35.

Savino, D. M. (2016). Frederick Winslow Taylor and his legacy of functional leadership competence. *Journal of Leadership, Accountability and Ethics*, 1(3), 70-76

Spacey, J. (2016). What is service delivery?
<https://simplicable.com/amp/service-delivery>.